

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, THERMAL PROPERTIES OF NOVEL PHENOLIC RESINS /SILICA NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The novel phenolic/silica hybrid ceramers were synthesized by sol-gel process. FTIR and ²⁹Si NMR were used to characterize the structure of the hybrids. Results revealed that Q⁴, Q³, T³ are the major microstructures, i.e., network structures were formed. SEM, TEM and Si mapping revealed the hybrids were nanocomposites. The thermal properties were investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The char yields of the hybrids increased with increasing TEOS content. T_{d5} (the degradation temperature of 5% weight loss) of the hybrid containing 20 wt % TEOS content was 290°C. As the TEOS content was increased to 80wt %, the T_{d5} of the hybrid rose to 312°C. TEOS inorganic components enhance the heat stability of hybrids. Limiting oxygen index (L.O.I.) and the UL-94 test revealed that the hybrid ceramer possesses excellent flame retardance.

KEYWORDS : phenolic resin, hybrid ceramer, sol-gel process, thermal property, nanocomposites, flame retardance

INTRODUCTION

The organic-inorganic hybrid materials are new types of composites, which have attracted much interest in recent years. Of the several kinds of inorganic components, metal oxides such as silica [1,2], alumina [3,4] and titania [5-8] are the most preferred in hybrid materials because they are readily prepared in-situ by the sol-gel process using the corresponding organic metal alkoxide. In particular, silicon alkoxide and silica are perhaps the most widely used for this purpose since the sol-gel reaction of silicon alkoxide is both mild and easily controlled. The fabricated materials possess the advantages of both organic polymers and inorganic ceramics. These materials are termed "Ceramers" by Wilkes [9] or "Ormosils" by Schmidt [10]. Several polymers have been investigated as the organic phase of the hybrids such as polyimides [11,12], polybutadiene and polydimethylsiloxane [13], and so on.

The sol-gel process [14-22] has provided promising opportunities for the preparation of a

1. Experimental

1.1 Materials

Phenol and formaldehyde monomers are supplied by the Union Chemical Works Ltd, Taiwan. The novolac-type phenolic resin was synthesized in this laboratory. Hexamethylenetetramine (hexamine) was a purified industry grade reagent obtained from Chu-Chung Resin Co., Taiwan. The concentrated sulfuric acid was obtained from the Osaka Chemical Co., Japan. Isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane was purchased from United Chemical Technologies Inc., Bristol, PA, U.S.A. Tetraethoxysilan (TEOS) was supplied from Acros Organics Co., Geel West Zone 2, Janssen Pharmaceuticaaan 3a, 2440 Geel, Belgium. Tetrahydrofuran was reagent grade supplied by Echo Chemical Co. Ltd., Taiwan.

2.2 Preparation of novolac phenolic resin

The novolac-type phenolic prepolymer was synthesized in a 1.0L glass reactor equipped with a thermometer, reflux condenser, and stirrer. The reagents, 188g phenol (2 mol) and 135g formalin (in 37 wt% water solution, 1.67 mol), were fed into a flask reactor. The reaction was catalyzed by adding diluted sulfuric acid solution (2g of sulfuric acid dissolved in 10 ml of water) and reacting at 100°C for 7 h in the reactor. The reaction was continued until the prepolymer with a desired viscosity (500-2000 cps at 25°C) was obtained. At the end of the reaction, the calculated amount (1.63g) of NaOH was dispersed in 10 ml of water and added to neutralize the sulfuric acid catalyst and then stirred for an additional 30 min. The mixture was dehydrated under a pressure of 100 mm H₂O at 120-130°C until the resin was clear.

2.3 Preparation of hybrid ceramers

Preparation of the hybrid ceramer involved mixing of two solutions, A and B. Solution A consisted of modified phenolic resin and THF. The modified phenolic resin was synthesized as follows: 4g 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane (equivalent weight 247g) was added into 10g phenolic resin (OH equivalent weight 90g) at 60°C, then it was stirred for 4 hours until the characteristic peak of NCO group disappeared by FTIR spectra. Solution B contained H₂O /HCl /TEOS with a molar ratio 9:0.63:1. HCl was used as the catalyst for hydrolysis. DGEBA type epoxy (epoxy equivalent weight 180g) was poured into the mixture of solution A and B. DGEBA type epoxy was used as the curing agent for the modified phenolic resin. 3-Isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane/ phenolic resin / epoxy with the equivalent ratio was 0.3:1:1. The mixture was stirred until the solution became clear. The solution was cast into aluminum dish to gel at room temperature. The wet gel was aged at room temperature for 48 h, then dried at 80°C for 24 h. The samples were put in a vacuum oven at 150°C for 24 h.

2.4 Reaction scheme

Phenolic/silica hybrid ceramer was prepared as described in scheme 1

Scheme 1

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization

Fig. 1 shows the FT-IR spectra of the reaction between novalac phenolic and 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane. The figure displays the change of the characteristic peak of NCO group of 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane at 2270cm^{-1} . Result reveals that novalac type phenolic resin has reacted with 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane at various times.

Fig. 2 shows the curve of solid-state ^{29}Si NMR spectra of phenolic nanocomposite. Condensed siloxane species for TEOS in which a silicon atom through mono-, di-, tri-, tetra-substituted siloxane bonds are designated as Q^1 , Q^2 , Q^3 , Q^4 , respectively. The definition of Q^s was shown as following:

The chemical shifts -91 , -101 , -109 ppm of Q^2 , Q^3 , Q^4 , respectively, are in good agreement with the literature data [26].

For 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilanes with mono-, di-, tri-, tetra-substituted siloxane bonds are designated as T^1 , T^2 , and T^3 . The definition of T^s was shown as following:

The chemical shifts -56 , -65 ppm of T^2 , T^3 , respectively, which confirm the literature values [27]. Results revealed that Q^4 , Q^3 , T^3 are the major environments, i.e., it formed network structure.

Fig.1 FT-IR spectra of the reaction between nocalac phenolic resin and 3-isocyanatopropyl triethoxysilane, at various reaction times: (a) initial reaction (b) 4 hr (c) 8 hr (d) 12 hr

Fig.2 The curve of solid-state ^{29}Si NMR spectra of phenolic hybrid ceramer

Thermal properties of hybrids

Fig. 3 shows the TGA curves of the hybrids for different TEOS compositions from room temperature to 800°C in the N_2 atmosphere. The char yields of the hybrids increase with increasing TEOS content. Increasing char formation can reduce the production of combustible gases, decreases the exothermicity during the pyrolysis reaction and inhibits the thermal conductivity of the burning materials【28】. As the TEOS content increases, the rates of degradation will be slower. The inorganic components can retard the degradation of the hybrids. The char yield has been correlated to the flame retardance【29】. Therefore, through the condensed phase mechanism, the flame retardancy of the hybrids is promoted. The inference would be discussed in the following LOI and UL-V test section. Fig. 4 presents T_{d5} (the degradation temperature of 5%weight loss) of the hybrids for different TEOS contents. Table 1 shows the T_{d5} of hybrid ceramer. When TEOS content was 20%, the T_{d5} of the hybrid is 290°C . As the TEOS content increases to 80%, T_{d5} of the hybrid raises to 312°C . TEOS inorganic components enhance the heat stability of hybrids. Figures 5 and 6 show the isothermal degradation curves of phenolic/silica hybrids at different temperatures. From Fig.5, it can be found that the hybrid containing 80% TEOS content at 200°C is very stable, it still maintains 93 wt% for 300 min. Even when it was kept at 800°C for 300 min, the weight retention is 45%. The hybrid exhibits good heat resistance. Fig. 6 exhibits the similar trend as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 7 presents the DSC thermograms of the phenolic/silica hybrid ceramers. From these curves, the glass transition temperature is not clear enough. It reveals that the networks of inorganic components restrict the motions of the chains. This result confirms

the data of ^{29}Si NMR spectra for the phenolic/silica hybrid ceramers. The hybrid ceramers possess the structures of networks. Table 1 summarizes the Tgs of phenolic/silica hybrid ceramers. The Tgs of the hybrid increased with the incorporation of inorganic components.

Fig. 3 TGA curves of phenolic resin/silica hybrid ceramer with various TEOS contents

Fig. 4 T_{d5} (the temperature of degradation at which the weight loss of material is 5%) of the hybrid with different TEOS contents

Fig. 5 The isothermal degradation curves of phenolic/silica hybrid ceramer for 60 wt % TEOS at different temperatures

Fig. 6 The isothermal degradation curves of phenolic/silica hybrid ceramer for 80 wt % TEOS at different temperatures

Fig. 7 DSC thermograms of phenolic resin/silica hybrid creamer

Table 1 Thermal properties of hybrid ceramer. with various TEOS content

System wt %TEOS	Glass transition temperature T _g (°C)	5% weight loss degradation temperature T _{d5} (°C)
20	140	290
40	152	300
60	-----	302
80	-----	312

Morphological properties

The compatibility of organic polymer and silica strongly affects the thermal, mechanical and optical properties of nanocomposites. The morphology of the fractured surfaces was observed by SEM, the mapping technique was utilized to elucidate the distribution of silica and the separation of microphase in the hybrid matrix. Figure 8 presents the SEM microphotograph of the nanocomposites. Figure 9 shows Si mapping of phenolic nanocomposites. In the figure, the white dots represent the silicon atoms. The transmission electron microphotograph (TEM) of phenolic nanocomposites was shown in Figure 10. The dark domains represent SiO₂ particles. According to SEM and TEM micrographs, the particles were uniformly dispersed throughout the polymer matrix with sizes below 100nm, indicating the hybrids are nanocomposites. This result revealed that the nanocomposites exhibit good miscibility between organic and inorganic phases.

Flame Retardance

The flame retardant properties of the obtained hybrids were examined by measuring the L.O.I. of the hybrids. From Table 2, one can find a significant increase in L.O.I. (from 33 to 44) was observed when TEOS was utilized in the phenolic resins. This indicates that incorporating silicon shows a significant effect on promoting the flame retardance of phenolic resins. This result is coincident with the char yield data. Moreover, the UL-94 test was also applied to probe the flame retardance of the hybrids and to rank them into an industrial expression. The results of UL-94 test are also shown in Table 1. From this Table, the neat phenolic resin may be classified into the UL-94 V-1. The hybrids containing 20 wt % TEOS content can be classified as UL-94 V-0 grade. The phenolic hybrids with good flame retardancy (L.O.I. : 32 ~ 44, UL94 V-0 grade) and excellent thermal stability (T_g is above 300°C) are considered to be sufficient for applications as green flame retardant materials.

Fig. 8 SEM of phenolic nanocomposites

Silicon Ka1

Fig. 9 Si mapping of phenolic nanocomposites

Fig 10 TEM of phenolic nanocomposites

Table 2 The UL-94 and L.O.I. test results of Novolac type phenolic/TEOS hybrids

TEOS content(wt%)	Flaming drops	Cotton ignited	UL-94 standard	L.O.I.
Neat phenolic	N/A*	N/A	94V-1	32
20	N/A	N/A	94V-0	35
40	N/A	N/A	94V-0	37
60	N/A	N/A	94V-0	40
80	N/A	N/A	94V-0	43

CONCLUSIONS

A novel phenolic/silica hybrid ceramer synthesized by sol-gel process has been demonstrated. FTIR and ^{29}Si NMR were used to characterize the structure of the hybrids. Results revealed that Q^4 , Q^3 , T^3 are the major environments, i.e. it formed the network structure. The thermal properties were investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The char yields of the hybrids increased with increasing TEOS contents. T_{d5} (the degradation temperature of 5% weight loss) of the hybrid containing 20% TEOS content was 290°C . As the TEOS content increases to 80%, T_{d5} of the hybrid is 312°C . TEOS

inorganic components enhance the heat stability of hybrids. Both SEM and TEM micrographs reveal that the particles were uniformly dispersed throughout the polymer matrix with sizes below 100nm, implying the hybrids are nanocomposites. L.O.I. and UL-94 V test results reveal that the hybrid ceramer possesses excellent flame retardance.

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